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Measuring innovation in the informal sector: Preliminary Findings

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Background

Understanding how to enhance enterprise-level innovativeness is important but this is not possible without reliable measurements on how firms innovate. However, innovation is generally difficult to measure, more so in the informal sector. The difficulties in measuring innovation in the informal sector are especially pronounced in developing countries such as Nigeria. Many firms in the sector are not visible to surveys, and their innovative activities are sometimes intractable to conventional measurement indicators (Mustapha et al, 2021). Yet, the informal sector remains an important economic sector in most developing countries. In Nigeria, for instance, estimates show that the approximately 65% of economic activities about 80% of private sector employment were in the informal sector in 2017 (IMF, 2015; Onwo, & Ohazulike, 2021). The informal sector is also characterized by ease of entry, low labour costs, operational flexibility, low capital requirements, but low skill and capabilities (ILO, 2001; Ulyssea, 2018).

Given the economic importance of the informal sector and the understanding that innovation is important for competitiveness (Feldmann, et al., 2019), we set out to measure innovation in the informal sector in Nigeria. We have implemented a survey of innovation in the formal sector since 2008 under the AU-NEPAD African Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators (ASTII) Initiative but this is the first time we will attempt to measure innovation in the informal sector. Following South Africa, Nigeria is now the second African country that has started to systematically track innovation in its informal sector in Africa.

The major challenge in measuring informal sector innovation is the non-availability of standardized, widely accepted instruments. The available standards and instruments, such as those of the Community Innovation Surveys (CIS) and their adaptations in Africa, are inappropriate for capturing the realities of the informal sector. To address this challenge, we adapted the Local Innovation and Production System (LIPS) framework (Casiolato et al, 2017). This framework was developed with the informal sector in mind and has been previously applied in Brazil and South Africa.

This paper seeks to present our ongoing work with a focus on the adaptation of the LIPS framework to the Nigerian context. We hope that this will stimulate interest and spur the debate on how innovation can be appropriately measured in informal sector enterprises. Ultimately, this will provide insight for the design and implementation of context-relevant interventions.

The innovation and production systems (LIPS) framework.

The LIPS framework covers the main elements of the local systems that condition the emergence and evolution of innovation (Table 1). In our study, we focus on productive and innovative capabilities of local firms within the informal sector in terms of knowledge assimilation, usage, and diffusion under the assumption that every geographical location holds some forms and levels of collaboration, interactions, production value chain, infrastructural support, and intellectual property. These territorial artifacts are linked to the economic activities to establish a systemic context which influences the nature and rate of innovative activity. Every territory is, in turn, embedded within a governing structure that organizes its systems of operations (Cassiolato, *et. al*, 2017). The complex interconnectedness of the LIPS elements is illustrated in Figure 1 (Mustapha *et al.* 2019)

Table 1: Description of LIPS framework

Pillars	Remarks	Indicators
Knowledge sharing and learning	the production and innovation capacity building processes within the innovation system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information sources for innovation Knowledge use in innovation Learning
innovation and development	the wider policy environment impacting on activities in the innovation system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Types of innovation Innovation activities Novelty and origin of innovation Obstacles to innovation
Territoriality and embeddedness	the national and international context in which the innovation system is embedded	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financing and knowledge infrastructure Physical infrastructure supporting innovation system Governance and exercise of power

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the LIPS model in the informal sector
Source: Mustapha et al. (2019)

Defining innovation in the informal sector.

In order to have a broad perspective of innovation, we adopt the broad definition of business innovation as defined by the 4th edition of the Oslo Manual. It defines business innovation as “a new or improved product or business process (or combination thereof) that differs significantly from the enterprise's previous products or business processes and that has been introduced on the market or brought into use by the enterprise” (OECD, 2018: 68). This definition emphasizes novelty at the firm level and is based on the broader Doing-User-Interaction (DUI) mode of learning of innovation; alluding to the general notion in literature that innovation in the informal sector is incremental.

Building upon this definition, innovation activities in the informal sector are captured in the following simple statements to which firms are expected to respond Yes/No:

- Look for and use new sources of supply of raw materials and tools
- Bring in know-how or other types of knowledge from other businesses
- Engage in a formal apprenticeship system (with certification at the end)
- Engage in on-the-job learning usually from a supervisor at work (without certification at the end of the training)
- Promote “happy accidents” (unexpected discovery) during production
- Find out if customers are satisfied with the current product; or if the customers are interested in new products or are willing to pay for it
- Bring in tools, machinery and equipment for the purpose of changing what the business produces or how it produces it

Approach to measuring innovation in the nigerian informal sector

Four business activities were selected for our study namely information and communication technologies (ICTs), shea butter production, metal fabrication, and leather works. This economic activities were selected because of their importance to economic activity in terms of employment and revenue generation in the country. They span business activities in the manufacturing, services and agricultural sectors. Our survey was conducted across the nation, covering the six (6) geopolitical regions and ten (10) states where these business activities are predominant.

Primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire and a total of 2000 respondents were reached with the aid of an online platform that is compatible with the web and mobile devices. The questionnaire was deployed with the help of enumerators who were proficient in local languages.

Preliminary Results

The study is exploratory in nature and we mostly use descriptive analysis. We argue that analysis such as this will help us better appreciate the complexities of the informal sector in the country. Through our results, we learnt that openness and adaptability proved to be effective strategies for the informal sector which allows them to adapt to competitive pressures. For instance, most of the enterprises in the informal sector utilize information from customers, suppliers and competitors as sources for innovation activities. Interestingly, our analysis revealed that informal enterprises in Nigeria are radical in their approach to process innovations while product innovations seem to be incremental. For instance, most of the enterprises surveyed reported to have completely changed the way they made or sold their goods and services. Some of them have also evolved new ways of letting people know about the products. Meanwhile, most of the products in the sector have only been improved upon from what they were before. Unfortunately, we noticed that most of the enterprises within the informal sector

have not really embraced digital technologies either as sources of information or strategies to promote their products and access to financial support is very poor as most of them depend on family and friends.

Emerging evidence has shown that innovation is critical to the growth and sustainability of the informal sector in Nigeria. However, greater improvements will come from institutionalizing policy-driven interactions among the key actors within the local innovation and production systems. In general, this study underscores the need to promote and enhance local system's openness and flexibility.

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